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Definition of scenarios on the basis of trends in relevant drivers.

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ABSTRACT

This report describes the results from Task 1.4 of the EJP SOIL SERENA project. The aim of this Task was to define relevant scenarios based on four main drivers: climate change, land use/land cover, land management, and demographic trends. The first part of the work comprised the analysis of both scientific literature and documents at global and EU level, and the identification of all important characteristics regarding trends and scenarios to be communicated to stakeholders. The second part dealt with methods for making stakeholders aware of general trends under different scenarios, and in encouraging cooperation in highlighting the most relevant trends for further development. To achieve this aim, a questionnaire was produced and distributed to stakeholders, and the results are presented in this report.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

BAU	Business as Usual
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
MS	Member States
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathways
SESs	Soil-based ecosystem services
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
ST	Soil threat
UN	United Nations
UNCBD	United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity
UNCCD	United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification

1 Introduction and Objectives

The need for good agro-management practices and techniques to contribute to the improvement of soil health and to mitigate the effects of and adapt to anticipated global change scenarios have been widely recognized. The predicted effects of global changes make it necessary to properly inform stakeholders about risks under future scenarios. To contribute to the improvement of soil health and to mitigate and adapt to the effects of global changes, it is important that people are made aware of the benefits of sustainable cropping systems and the implementation of beneficial for the soil agro-management practices and techniques.

Task 1.4 focuses on defining, from available scientific knowledge, and providing, with the collaboration of stakeholders, the relevant scenarios that climate change, demographic trends, and changes in land use/land cover and land management could produce in agricultural soils. The main objective of Task 1.4 is to make stakeholders aware of general trends under different scenarios and to involve them in identifying those with the potential to mitigate the effects that these scenarios foresee.

Task 1.4 was implemented in two steps:

- 1) the identification of scenarios based on four main drivers: climate change, demographic trends, land use/land cover and land management, based on the analysis of documents at global and EU level, and scientific literature.
- 2) the cooperation of stakeholders in co-constructing the relevant scenarios, that these four drivers could produce in agricultural soils. Based on the scenarios developed in step 1, a questionnaire was produced and distributed to stakeholders. Answers were analysed, summarised, and graphically represented.

This report describes the results of these two steps.

2 Methodology

2.1 Identification of Scenarios

The identification of scenarios was based on a literature review regarding:

- i. institutional and large organization documents (UN/global/EU documents);
- ii. searches in scientific literature, resulting from the activity developed in Task 3.3 of the SERENA project.

A table was drafted to summarize the key information of the analysed documents. The table had the following structure:

- **Information:** name of the authors or the organisation, journal/report name, year of publication, reference (web link, DOI, etc.), level of the analysis (global, continental, regional, etc.), country of the study area, region of the study area.
- **Characteristic of the study:** the type of scenarios analysed (climate, land use/cover, land management, demographic trend), a description of the scenarios, method of assessment, name of the model used, start and end date of the assessment, time scale of the projection used, identified trends and the form of the results of the assessment (map, scientific publication, report, etc.)
- **Information regarding soil threats (ST), soil-based ecosystem services (SEs) and soil indicators involved, following the Task 3.1 list of the SERENA project.**

Field name	Description
Authors/Organisation	Name of the authors or the organisation
Journal/Report	Journal/Report name
Year	Year of publication
Reference	Web links, DOI, etc.
Level	Level of the analysis (global, continental, regional, etc.)
Country	Country of the study area
Region	Region of the study area
Type_scenario	Climate, land use/land cover, land management, demographic trend
Description	Description of scenarios
Method	Method of assessment
For models only: Which model is used?	Name of the model used
Time period of the assessment	Start and end date of the assessment
Time projection	Time scale of the projection used
Trends	Identified trends
Form of the outputs	Form of the results of the assessment (map, scientific publication, report, etc.)
Sector impacted	Type of sector impacted (agriculture, forest, landscape, etc.)
Soil threats	Soil threats involved
Soil-based ES	Soil-based ecosystem services involved
Soil indicators	Relevant soil indicators

Figure 1 - Structure of Task 1.4 table to summarize information about the documents analysed

As regards the institutional and large organization literature, the selection was based on the main documents regarding scenarios analysis; in particular: Global Land Outlook (2 reports), the Copernicus programme, the ESPON programme, IPCC reports, FAO reports and European research projects.

The scientific literature was selected from the studies collected in Task 3.3 regarding ST and SESs, with consideration to the four drivers selected for analysis.

As a result of the document collection phase, a total of 30 potential sources was compiled. This list was subsequently screened to select those with both the most complete information possible (Appendix 1) and containing the relevant characteristics regarding trends and scenarios to be communicated to and discussed with stakeholders.

2.2 Questionnaire Drafting

Based on the results obtained from the literature review analysis, a survey phase was planned to investigate stakeholder opinions. The aim was to incorporate the views of representatives from public administrations, policy makers, organizations (e.g., associations, NGOs, etc.), and farmers.

It was decided to use a semi-structured interview, with a series of questions prepared around some guiding themes, but with such flexibility as to allow stakeholders to express their opinions. The format of the survey was as follows:

- At the beginning of the questionnaire, an introduction was included, to explain the reason and the aim of the survey.
- To get deeper insights about drivers and scenarios of change, the first part of the survey included some questions about the stakeholder's opinion on the importance of SESs, ST and drivers of change, followed by questions about their agreement on strategies and practices to adopt or avoid selected scenarios of change. Towards the end of the survey, questions related to the stakeholder's willingness or ability to adapt to environmental changes by modifying policies or practices.

- A Likert scale approach with a rating scheme of four-point scales was chosen (Allen and Seaman, 2007).
- The list of choices included responses relating to agreement (strongly disagree, somewhat disagree, somewhat agree, strongly agree), importance (not important, slightly important, Important, very important), and value (very low, low, high, very high).
- The questionnaire was prepared in English and then translated into 13 languages thanks to the support of SERENA partners: Dutch, Lithuanian, Portuguese, Polish, Latvian, Hungarian, French, Estonian, Slovak, Spanish, Norwegian, German, and Italian.
- The online platform Google Forms was used to upload the questionnaires. The questionnaire was distributed to stakeholders whose names and emails were provided by the SERENA Stakeholder Database and the Policy Stakeholders contact list of EJP SOIL WP8. Others were contacted by the National Communication Representatives and during meetings held in Italy and Austria; or thanks to the collaboration of the national soil science societies.

The questionnaire in English may be viewed [here](#) and the full questionnaire is attached in Appendix 2.

3 Results

3.1 Overview of the Selected Documents

After the screening step, 20 studies were chosen, mainly carried out at a global scale (10 studies), national level (8 studies) and continental levels of analysis (8 studies). The time projections most frequently analysed were 2050 (10 studies) and 2100 (8 studies). Most of the studies address climate and land management as drivers of change (18 and 16 studies respectively), followed by land use/cover (10 studies) and population trends (4 studies). The bulk of the studies dealt with soil organic carbon loss (9 studies), soil erosion as ST (6 studies), GHG/climate regulation including carbon sequestration (12 studies), Primary/biomass production (9 studies), and Hydrological control as SESs (9 studies) (Table 1).

Table 1 - Main results from the literature review

	FACTORS CONSIDERED	NUMBER OF STUDIES
SPATIAL LEVEL OF ANALYSIS	Global	10
	Continental	8
	Regional	2
	National	8
	Local	2
TIME PROJECTION	2030	5
	2040	5
	2050	10
	2060	2
	2070	4
	2080	3
	2100	8
DRIVERS	Climate	18
	Land management	16

	Land use/land cover	10
	Demographic trend	4
SOIL THREATS	Soil organic carbon loss	9
	Soil erosion	6
	Nutrient imbalances	3
	Soil compaction	3
	Loss of diversity	3
	Soil acidification	2
	Soil contamination	2
	Soil sealing	1
	Waterlogging	1
SOIL-BASED ECOSYSTEM SERVICES	GHG/climate regulation including carbon sequestration	12
	Primary/biomass production	9
	Hydrological control	9
	Habitat for biodiversity	5
	Erosion control	5

The scenarios identified in the literature reviewed is summarised in Table 2.

Table 2 - Summary of scenarios from literature reviewed

<p>Van der Esch et al. 2021 Scenarios for the Global Land Outlook 2 (PBL 2022) Description: Estimates of land degradation. Drivers: climate, land use/land cover, land management, demographic trend Time projection: 2050 BASELINE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - no additional efforts are made to restore or protect land resources - T increase 1.4–2.5 °C by the year 2050 - Population from 7.4 to 9.3 billion people - Income from 12,200 to 27,600 USD per capita - Crop production from 4,570 to 6,620 million tonnes - Livestock production from 300 to 430 million tonnes - Cereal yields from 3.5 to 4.1 t/ha <p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 16 million km² of land degraded - 60-70 gigatons/year of CO₂ emissions - agricultural yields slowing - biodiversity suffering <p>RESTORATION:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - land restoration on a massive scale – 50 million km² - all areas identified as having less soil organic carbon than under natural conditions or declining trends in primary productivity can potentially be restored <p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Crop yields increase by 5-10% in most developing countries - Carbon stocks rise by a net 17 gigatonnes
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- Slowed biodiversity decline and loss of natural land

RESTORATION & PROTECTION:

- measures expanded to cover close to half of the Earth's land surface by 2050
- key areas to be, based on the key ecosystem services of carbon storage, biodiversity, crop yields, livestock production, water availability and water regulation

Output:

- An additional four million km² of natural land
- Carbon stocks rise by 83 gigatonnes and emissions fall by 13%

IPCC 2019

Special report, Climate Change and Land

DESCRIPTION: The implications of future socio-economic development on climate change mitigation, adaptation and land-use are explored using shared socio-economic pathways (SSPs). The SSPs span a range of challenges to climate change mitigation and adaptation.

Drivers: climate, land use, land management, demographic trend

Time projection: 2050 and 2100

SSP1 includes a peak and decline in population (~7 billion in 2100), high income and reduced inequalities, effective land use regulation, less resource intensive consumption, including food produced in low-GHG emission systems and lower food waste, free trade and environmentally friendly technologies and lifestyles. Relative to other pathways, SSP1 has low challenges to mitigation and low challenges to adaptation (i.e., high adaptive capacity)

Output:

- continued, but moderate, climate change: global mean temperature increases by 3 to 3.5°C in 2100
- low levels of food insecurity: malnourishment is eliminated by 2050
- declines in biodiversity: biodiversity loss increases from 34% in 2010 to 38% in 2100
- high water stress: global water withdrawals decline slightly from the baseline in 2071–2100, but about 2.6 billion people live in water stressed areas
- additionally, this scenario is likely to have lower challenges related to desertification, land degradation, and biodiversity loss than SSP2 as it has lower population, lower land-use change and lower climate change

SSP2 includes medium population growth (~9 billion in 2100), medium income, technological progress, production and consumption patterns are a continuation of past trends, and only a gradual reduction in inequality occurs. Relative to other pathways, SSP2 has medium challenges to mitigation and medium challenges to adaptation (i.e., medium adaptive capacity)

Output:

- continued climate change: global mean temperature increases by 3.8°C to 4.3°C in 2100
- increased challenges related to desertification: the population living in drylands is expected to increase by 43% in 2050
- increased land degradation: soil organic carbon is expected to decline by 99 GtCO₂e in 2050
- low levels of food insecurity: malnourishment is eliminated by 2100
- declines in biodiversity: biodiversity loss increases from 34% in 2010 to 43% in 2100
- high water stress: global water withdrawals nearly double from the baseline in 2071–2100, with about 4 billion people living in water stressed areas

SSP3 includes high population growth (~13 billion in 2100), low income and continued inequalities, material-intensive consumption and production, barriers to trade, and slow rates of technological change. Relative to other pathways, SSP3 has high challenges to mitigation and high challenges to adaptation (i.e., low adaptive capacity)

Output:

- continued climate change: global mean temperature increases by 4°C to 4.8°C in 2100
- high levels of food insecurity: about 600 million malnourished in 2100
- declines in biodiversity: biodiversity loss increases from 34% in 2010 to 46% in 2100
- high water stress: global water withdrawals more than double from the baseline in 2071–2100, with about 5.5 billion people living in water stressed areas
- additionally, this scenario is likely to have higher challenges to desertification, land degradation, and biodiversity loss than SSP2 as it has higher population, higher land-use change and higher climate change

SSP4 includes medium population growth (~9 billion in 2100), medium income, but significant inequality within and across regions. Relative to other pathways, SSP4 has low challenges to mitigation, but high challenges to adaptation (i.e., low adaptive capacity)

Output:

- continued climate change: global mean temperature increases by 3.4°C to 3.8°C in 2100
- high levels of food insecurity: about 400 million malnourished in 2100
- high water stress: about 3.5 billion people live in water stressed areas in 2100
- additionally, this scenario is likely to have similar effects on biodiversity loss as SSP2 as it has similar land-use change and similar climate change

SSP5 includes a peak and decline in population (~7 billion in 2100), high income, reduced inequalities, and free trade. This pathway includes resource-intensive production, consumption and lifestyles. Relative to other pathways, SSP5 has high challenges to mitigation, but low challenges to adaptation (i.e., high adaptive capacity)

Output:

- continued climate change: global mean temperature increases by 4.6°C to 5.4°C in 2100
- low levels of food insecurity: malnourishment is eliminated by 2050 – increased water use and water scarcity: global water withdrawals increase by about 80% in 2071–2100, with nearly 50% of the population living in water stressed areas
- additionally, this scenario is likely to have higher effects on biodiversity loss as SSP2 as it has similar land-use change and higher climate change

IPCC 2022

Shared Socio-Economic Pathways

DESCRIPTION: The Shared Socio-Economic Pathways SSP1 and SSP2 were structured to explore futures with socio-economic challenges to adaptation and mitigation increasing from low to high, while SSP5 explored a world with low challenges to adaptation but high challenges to mitigation.

Driver: climate change, land management

Time projection: 2100

SSP1:

- 1.5°C by 2050
- Global CO2 emissions are cut to net zero around 2050
- Societies switch to more sustainable practices
- Investments in education and health go up. Inequality falls

SSP2: “middle of the road”: CO2 emissions hover around current levels before starting to fall mid-century, but do not reach net-zero by 2100

SSP5:

- current CO2 emissions levels roughly double by 2050
- the global economy grows quickly, but this growth is fuelled by exploiting fossil fuels and energy-intensive lifestyles
- 4.4°C by 2100

Output: SSP1 and SSP5 foreshadow the most optimistic scenarios for humanity, with "substantial investments in education and health, rapid economic growth, and well-functioning institutions." The

main difference between them is that SSP5 postulates that these advances will be driven by an energy-intensive economy, based on fossil fuels, while in SSP1 sustainable practices will prevail. The middle ground is represented by SSP2, in which historical development models continue throughout the twenty-first century

FAO 2018

Alternative pathways to 2050

DESCRIPTION: Under the assumption that agriculture should contribute proportionally to changes in emissions and given that in 2012 global agricultural systems emitted around 5.2 gigatonnes of CO₂eq, and changing climate conditions lead to regional variations in future land suitability for crop production, the different scenarios designed for this foresight exercise therefore portray various possibilities of additional land available for cropping.

Driver: climate

Time projection: 2050

BAU: (associated with RCP 6.0) emissions would not exceed 8.0 gigatonnes CO₂eq in 2050

Output:

- GHG emissions from agricultural sectors increase by 24%
- Land requirements increase from 1567 million ha in 2012 to 1732 million ha (+ 11%)

TSS: (associated with RCP 4.5):

- emissions between 3.2 and 6.4 gigatonnes of CO₂eq in 2050
- sustainable production and consumption patterns

Output:

- GHG reduction of 39% in emissions

SSS: emissions exceed 8.5 gigatonnes of CO₂eq by the end of the period

Output:

- GHG emissions from agricultural sectors increase by 54%
- Land requirements increase from 1567 million ha in 2012 to 1892 million ha (+ 21%)

FAO 2021

The Impact of disasters and crises on agriculture and food security

DESCRIPTION: simulated crop productivity under future climate data (Uruguay, Malawi, and Zambia).

Driver: climate

Time projection: 2040 and 2070

SHORT TERM: A maximum temperature increase of 1 °C will decrease maize yields by 0.53 tonnes/ha and each decrease of 1 mm in total precipitation will decrease maize yields by 0.0043 tonnes/ha

LONG TERM: changes in maximum temperature up to 1.2 °C decreases yield by 0.64 tonnes/ha; while increases in rainfall, predicted to rise to 80 mm, increases yield by 0.34 tonnes

FAO 2022

Global Soil Organic Carbon Sequestration Potential Map

DESCRIPTION: SOC stocks in 0-30 cm of soils for agricultural areas by predicting changes in SOC stocks over a period of 20 years under a business as usual (BAU) scenario and three Sustainable Soil Management (SSM) scenarios that vary in the degree of carbon inputs to the soil.

Driver: land management

Time projection: 2040

BAU: projected soil organic carbon stocks after 20 years of business as usual

SSM1: projected soil organic carbon stocks in 2040, after 20 years of implementation of SSM practices that generate a 5% increase in carbon inputs

SSM2: projected soil organic carbon stocks in 2040, after 20 years of implementation of SSM practices that generate a 10% increase in carbon inputs

SSM3: projected soil organic carbon stocks in 2040, after 20 years of implementation of SSM practices that generate a 20% increase in carbon inputs

Trolard et al. 2016

PRECOS framework: Measuring the impacts of the global changes on soils, water, agriculture on territories to better anticipate the future (2016)

DESCRIPTION: in La Crau area (France) between 1997-2009 over 1600 ha agricultural and natural areas were lost to urban sprawl.

Driver: climate, land use, land management

Time projection: 2030

Scenario 0: Called "trend" scenario is the BAU scenario

Output: + 4377 ha will be lost by 2030

Scenario 1: Called the "industrial consolidation and diversification" scenario, assumes a strong industrial development

Output: More agricultural land lost (> 7000 ha)

Scenario 2: Called the "development of services and residential activities" scenario, assumes an important development in services such as logistics and residential activities dedicated to the tourism

Output:

- More agricultural land lost (> 7000 ha), less irrigation water is required
- Groundwater level decrease and there will be shortage of drinking water, esp. in urban area

Copernicus 2021

What-if analysis tool for soil erosion in Italy from 1981 to 2080

DESCRIPTION: tool for end-users to explore how land use and management can impact soil loss under different climate scenarios. Soil loss indicator is obtained by elaborating, in combination with land-based datasets, rainfall time series from the ERA5-Land climate reanalysis (for the 30-year reference period 1981-2010) and an ensemble of bias-corrected EURO-CORDEX simulations for near future (2021-2050) and far future (2051-2080) 30-year climatological periods under alternative Representative Concentration Pathways for greenhouse gases (RCPs 2.6, 4.5 and 8.5).

Drivers: Climate, Land cover, Land management

Time projection: Near future (2021-2050) Far future (2051-2080)

Results depend on the input user-selected factors on 'land cover and management for arable lands' or 'support practices'

EC 2018

A European long-term strategic vision for a prosperous, modern, competitive and climate neutral economy help meet EU food system policy targets

DESCRIPTION: Considers economy-wide scenarios whose main drivers are either the uptake of different technological options/innovative practices alone or enhanced by change in lifestyles and consumer behaviors. Four types of scenarios are considered to reflect the two objectives of the Paris Agreement (2030 and 2050).

Drivers: Climate; land use/land cover change and land management (in terms of lifestyle change in diets and technological upscaling)

Time projection: 5 years time-step

1) One BASELINE scenario: reflecting the 2030 targets of the EU Climate and Energy policies, projected to 2050 and beyond (2070). Corresponds to EU reference scenario published in 2016, which reaches 45% GHG emission reduction by 2030 and 60% emission reductions by 2050 (compared to 1990)

2) Five WELL BELOW 2° C scenarios: pursuing the well below 2° C target of the Paris Agreement through 80% GHG emission reductions by 2050. They consist in the uptake of technical mitigation

measures focusing on max levels of uptake of differently prioritized technologies for alternative energy sources or for the circular economy, with only very limited consideration of negative emission technologies

3) One COMBINATION scenario, that optimally combines the technological mitigation options of the well-below 2° C scenarios to achieve 90% reduction of GHG emissions by 2050

4) Two NET-ZERO scenarios pursuing the 1,5° C target (100% emission reduction). One of these relies on negative emission technologies (BECSS and DACSS); the other considers the enhancement of the carbon sinks in different ecosystems combined with change in diets across Europe

The models used support the representation of technological measures and shifts in demand patterns as well as the estimation of GHG and other emissions and the respective environmental, economic, or social/well-being impacts. The selection of technologies and shifts in demand patterns has been supported by an apriori public consultation on the Climate strategy of the EU

The options impacting the SESs or the STs relate to:

(a) the upscaling of technical options and practices for farm management leading to the reduction of non-CO2 GHGs from agriculture (considered in one of the "well below 2° C" scenarios implementing circular economy as well as in the subsequent COMBO and or to maintenance/enhancement of SOC stocks

(b) the shifts in demand patterns for biomass as energy or industrial feedstock (together with constraints on imports of biomass) considered across all alternative scenarios.

(c) the shifts in demand for food products (diets) together with reduction of food waste and constraints on imports, considered in the last scenario

The scenarios consider only mitigation options for reducing GHGs, but the publication highlights the need to integrate them with adaptation scenarios since changing climate impacts can undermine mitigation efforts by impacting on the capacity of ecosystems to provide services to the society or to agriculture, which could invalidate some of the assumptions (e.g. yield increases, etc.)

Poux, X., Aubert, P.M. 2018

Ten Years for Agroecology (TYFA) in Europe project

DESCRIPTION: 5 modules of the model representing (1) crop production (land use and yields) (2) livestock production (land use competition between demand for food and feed); (3) demand for food; (4) industrial demand other than food; (5) nitrogen flows between the 4 modules as a major component for soil fertility. Scenarios are based on: a) land use/land management at plot and landscape level, b) redesign of livestock, c) reduction of industrial and energy land uses, d) sustainable diets.

Drivers: climate, land use/land cover, land management, demographic trend

Time projection: 2050

Scenario Baseline: 2010 state of land use patterns, of crop and animal production, diets, population, industrial demand, trade flows, climate and nitrogen cycling

Scenario TYFA 2050: assumptions of changes in demand for food, crop and animal production, industrial demand, trade flows and climate

Scenario TYFA 2050 + GHG: TYFA + climate neutrality (greater reduction of bovine livestock + increase of biogas production from side streams)

Output:

- Crop production decrease (-30% kcal equivalent) due to extensive land and livestock management, but plant-based diets allow to cover food demand
- Livestock production declines by 40% (granivores and pigs), while beef production is maintained (through extensification of dairy herds)
- Reduced use of grain maize and imported proteins
- Small variations in land use, the main differences occur within the arable land category
- In 2010 non-productive land has a function of an "ecological compensation" within an intensive agricultural landscape. In 2050 it is part of the extensive agricultural approach adopted in supporting biodiversity and enhancing the provision of ecosystem services

- Nitrogen balance: slight surplus of inputs
- GHG emissions: main reductions in agricultural soils, animal feed, and production of nitrogen
- Biodiversity: recreation of trophic chains and habitats

Röös et al. 2022

Agroecological practices in combination with healthy diets can help meet EU food system policy targets

DESCRIPTION: features for the agricultural sector in EU, with respect to a) trade and level of adoption of agroecological practices, b) plausible options for dietary preferences, innovation development and policy changes. Five trade/agricultural management scenarios have been investigated, also considering policy options which need to be put in place to achieve each of the five trade/agricultural management scenarios.

Drivers: climate, land use/land cover, land management, demographic trend

Time projection: 2050

Business-as-usual (BaU): low adoption of agroecological practices. Current globalisation trend in trade, current policy trend and current dietary trends in EU

Output:

- 3% reduction of cropland and 35% reduction of grazing land because of increases in yields and livestock productivity. 17% more land freed for regrowth of natural vegetation
- Food production: 15% increase in ruminant meat production due current dietary trends and increase in demand in EU and in the rest of the world. Reduction in the production of monogastric livestock products, eggs and dairy due to decrease in exports to the rest of the world; Increases in the production of most crops due to assumed increases in yields (45% cereals, 44% pulses, 48% oil crops, 73% root& tubers, 7% fruits, nuts & vgs). Potential auto sufficiency (EU level): 146%
- Environmental impacts:
 - (a) Climate: 13% increase in GHG emissions; 46% decrease in GHG emissions with carbon sequestration offsetting due to native vegetation regrowth in freed land
 - (b) Energy: 6% decrease in energy use
 - (b) Water: 40% increase in water use and 45% in water scarcity
 - (c) Pollution: 13% increase in pesticide use, 217% increase in N surplus and 5% increase in NH3 emissions
 - (d) Biodiversity: 21% increase in biomass appropriation; 10% increase in grazing intensity; Decrease in Shannon index in all regions (lower heterogeneity of agricultural land use) due to further intensification and specialisation in the BAU

Agroecology for Export: current dietary trends and the expansion of organic land management for increasing trade, creating a highly segmented market for organic products across Europe. In this scenario the organically managed land expands but only for the purpose of domestic consumption

Output:

- Land use: similar to BAU but most of the freed-up land is used to grow high quality products for export (1% decrease in cropland; 4% decrease in grazing land; 2% increase in freed land).
- Food Production: Increase in ruminant meat (13%), cereals (16%), pulses (14%), oilcrops (17%), roots&tubers (35%), fruits&nuts&vegs (223%). Decrease in pig&poultry meat (6%), eggs (32%), dairy (18%). Potential auto sufficiency (EU level): 110%
- Environmental impacts:
 - (a) Climate: 7% increase in GHG emissions; 63% decrease in GHG emissions with carbon sequestration offsetting due to native vegetation regrowth in freed land
 - (b) Energy: 9% increase in energy use
 - (c) Water: 49% increase in water use and 45% in water scarcity
 - (d) Pollution: 24% decrease in pesticide use, 25% increase in N surplus and 5% increase in NH3 emissions

(e) Biodiversity: 18% increase in biomass appropriation; 89% increase in grazing intensity; Decrease in Shannon index in all regions (lower heterogeneity of agricultural land use) due to the focus on high-value products for export

Localisation for protectionism: current levels of agroecological management, higher self-sufficiency in agricultural production by intensification in technology development and not through expansion of agricultural land. Low imports from the rest of the world

Output:

- Land use: like BAU (slightly more grazing land freed due to spatial redistribution of livestock, intensification of grazing and slight waste reduction).
- Food production: Increase in ruminant meat (13%), pulses (61%), oilcrops (221%), root&tubers (68%), fruits&nuts&vegs (16%). Decrease in pig&poultry meat (7%), eggs (33%), dairy (19%), cereals (8%). Potential auto sufficiency (EU level): 152%
- Environmental impacts:
 - (a) Climate: 15% increase in GHG emissions; 68% decrease in GHG emissions with carbon sequestration offsetting due to native vegetation regrowth in freed land
 - (b) Energy: 14% decrease in energy use
 - (c) Water: 25% increase in water use and 25% in water scarcity
 - (d) Pollution: 5% increase in pesticide use, 167% increase in N surplus and 9% decrease in NH3 emissions
 - (e) Biodiversity: 5% increase in biomass appropriation; 22% increase in grazing intensity; Moderate increase in Shannon index in all regions since domestic demand is the main driver in crop production

Localisation for sustainability: sustainable intensification practices, higher self-sufficiency. Shift in diets to match locally available food during seasons, diminishing meat and livestock products in South Europe). Rapid technological development and introduction of novel foods on the market.

Output:

- Land use: freeing-up 29% cropland and 72% grazing land due to productivity improvements, drastic diet changes and waste reductions
- Food production: Increase in pulses (492%), oilcrops (93%), root&tubers (2%), fruits&nuts&vegs (83%). Decrease in ruminant meat (66%), pig&poultry meat (73%), eggs (63%), dairy (69%), cereals (46%). Potential auto sufficiency (EU level): 203%
- Environmental impacts (with respect to baseline in 2012):
 - (a) Climate: 45% decrease in GHG emissions; 254% decrease in GHG emissions with carbon sequestration offsetting due to native vegetation regrowth in freed land
 - (b) Energy: 51% decrease in energy use
 - (c) Water: 29% increase in water use and 51% in water scarcity
 - (d) Pollution: 20% decrease in pesticide use, 200% increase in N surplus and 56% decrease in NH3 emissions
 - (e) Biodiversity: 43% decrease in biomass appropriation; 7% decrease in grazing intensity; Substantial increase in Shannon index in all regions since domestic demand change in pattern and since it is the main driver of crop production

Local agro-ecological food systems: high level adoption of agroecological practices, abolish industrial livestock, shift to plant-based diet, development of technological innovations, the farming system can provide and maintain in time high levels of supply of ecosystem services from agro-ecosystems

Output:

- Land use: 32% decrease in cropland and 13% decrease in grazing land due to yield increase as well as drastic change in diets and waste (the difference with 4) is in the degree of diffusion of agroecological practices and cropping systems, which are more extensive but also with low environmental impacts compared to sustainable intensification assumed in 4)
- Food Production: Increase in pulses (492%), oilcrops (53%), root&tubers (2%), fruits&nuts&vegs (83%). Decrease in ruminant meat (37%), pig&poultry meat (85%), eggs (81%), dairy (63%), cereals (56%). Potential auto sufficiency (EU level): 227%

- Environmental impacts:

(a) Climate: 47% decrease in GHG emissions; 164% decrease in GHG emissions with carbon sequestration offsetting due to native vegetation regrowth in freed land

(b) Energy: 34% decrease in energy use

(c) Water: 17% increase in water use and 38% in water scarcity

(d) Pollution: 57% decrease in pesticide use, 85% decrease in N surplus and 57% decrease in NH₃ emissions

(e) Biodiversity: 31% decrease in biomass appropriation; 32% increase in grazing intensity; High Shannon index in all regions due to change in demand patterns, focus on domestic demand, as well as higher penetration of agroecological practices

Gottschalk et al. 2012

How will organic carbon stocks in mineral soils evolve under future climate? Global projections using RothC for a range of climate change scenarios

DESCRIPTION: soil carbon model (RothC), driven by a range of climate models (AOGCM) for a range of SRES climate scenarios to examine the impacts of future climate on global soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks.

Drivers: climate, land use

Time projection: 2100

4 Scenarios: A1b, A2, B1 and B2

Output: overall global increase in SOC stocks by 2100 under all scenarios, but with a different extent of increase among the climate model and emissions scenarios. Underlying the global trend of increasing SOC under future climate is a complex pattern of regional SOC change. SOC losses are projected to occur in northern latitudes where higher SOC decomposition rates due to higher temperatures are not balanced by increased net primary production (NPP), whereas in tropical regions, NPP increases override losses due to higher SOC decomposition. The impacts of projected land use changes are also simulated but have relatively minor impacts at the global scale

Krause et al. 2019

Multimodel Analysis of Future Land Use and Climate Change Impacts on Ecosystem Functioning

DESCRIPTION: Three combinations of Shared Socioeconomic Pathways and Representative Concentration Pathways (SSP1xRCP26, SSP3xRCP60, and SSP5xRCP85) as input to three dynamic global vegetation models, i.e. multiple model approach (DGVMs; i.e. LPJ-GUESS, LPJ, and CABLE-POP models) to assess among of others SOC storage and losses.

Drivers: climate, land use

Time projection: 2080-2099

Output: Future climate change typically increases carbon stocks in vegetation but not soils, while future land use change causes carbon losses, even for net agricultural abandonment (SSP1xRCP26). The study indicated that there is a large spatial variance across scenarios and models considering carbon storage by the 2080–2099 period

Haas et al. 2022

Long term impact of residue management on soil organic carbon stocks and nitrous oxide emissions from European croplands

DESCRIPTION: The ensemble of three ecosystem models (CERES-EGC; Landscape-DNDC; Landscape-MeTrx) were applied to evaluate the effects of crop residue management in the EU-27. Four different residue management scenarios were defined and evaluated. Two climate projection scenarios (Representative Concentration Pathways, RCP) RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 were used in this study.

Drivers: climate, land management

Time projection: 2100

Baseline: residue management was defined as a function of the crop species, thereby using information on residues left on the field in different regions of Europe provided by FAO (Carozzi et al., 2021). Tillage was simulated 7 days before seeding

Exported: 80% of all above ground residues for all crops were assumed to be removed at harvest, i.e. leaving 20% of straw in form of stubbles on the field (the stubbles left by harvest machinery). Tillage was simulated 7 days before seeding

Buried: All above ground residues remained on the field and were incorporated into the top 20 cm of the soil by tillage 10 days after harvest. Tillage was simulated 7 days before seeding

Surface: All above ground residues remain on the field and were left on the soil Surface for decomposition. No-tillage was simulated after harvest

Output: While for the Exported scenario SOC content depletes over time, increases in topsoil SOC stocks were simulated for the Surface and Buried scenario, with the increase being higher under RCP 4.5 as compared to RCP8.5. The strongest SOC sequestration potential was associated with the Surface scenario (all residues applied to the soil Surface, reduced tillage). Climate change had a significant effect on SOC stocks with average SOC levels being 2–3% lower under RCP8.5 as compared to RCP4.5

Monforti et al. 2015

Optimal energy use of agricultural crop residues preserving soil organic carbon stocks in Europe

DESCRIPTION: Climate projections were derived from Global Climate Models (GCMs) forced by the four IPCC SRES scenarios. The projected SOC values were run with two contrasting scenarios, namely HadCM3-A1FI ('world markets fossil fuel intensive') and PCM-B1 ('global sustainability') as encompassing a wide range of climatic variations.

Drivers: climate, land management

Time projection: 2050

BAU scenario:

Output: areas in Europe are expected to react in a different way to BAU residues collection scenario in interaction with climate change: some areas SOC will deplete, in others not

No crop residue removal (R0):

Output: for 2020 shows that no collection is expected to end up in a constant or increasing SOC content almost everywhere in Europe. Same for 2050

Total crop residue removal (R100):

Output: full collection of residues is expected to negatively affect the SOC content almost everywhere in Europe, except for a few small areas. Same for 2050

Sonderegger et al. 2020

Assessing Impacts on the Natural Resource Soil in Life Cycle, Assessment: Methods for Compaction and Water Erosion

DESCRIPTION: considered impacts: compaction stress; shares [w%] of compaction losses in total global productivity losses; Characterization factor for (A) topsoil compaction, (B) mid soil compaction. Static modelling (empirical), baseline scenario (2000), no timesteps; TONKM: compaction model based on tonne-kilometre (tkm)

Drivers: land management

Output: soil productivity losses due to compaction. Results show that in a highly mechanized scenario of global agriculture without any conservation measures, long-term yearly soil productivity losses due to compaction and water erosion can amount to up to double-digit percentages for major crops. This confirms the relevance of compaction and water erosion impacts for agricultural LCAs

Hartmann et al. 2012

Effect of compaction, tillage and climate change on soil water balance of Arable-Luvisols in Northwest Germany

DESCRIPTION: conventional and conservation tillage systems compared. Based on regional A1B climate change scenarios the water balance was modelled with HYDRUS 1D for three different periods of 60/40 years (1991–2000; 2051–2060; 2091–2100) (static model).

Drivers: climate, land management

Time projection: 2051–2060; 2091–2100

Output: increase of actual transpiration rates in the growing period. Because of stronger drying and changed hydraulic properties, rewetting in autumn and winter was retarded and less complete on average. Furthermore, simulations indicated an increase of the variability of matric potentials. Consequently, compaction might result in a higher drought risk and a higher susceptibility for water logging in spring, which may result in less favourable soil conditions and plant growth

Bonfante et al. 2019

Refining physical aspects of soil quality and soil health when exploring the effects of soil degradation and climate change on biomass production: an Italian case study

DESCRIPTION: Climate change RCP 8.5 scenario; WAP is an integrated physically based simulation model of water, solute and heat transport in the saturated–unsaturated zone in relation to crop growth were run considering a soil without assumed degradation phenomena (the reference) and for three variants with a compacted plow layer, surface runoff and erosion (e.g. different rooting depths). Compaction is relevant considering the highly specialized and intensive horticulture land use of the Sele Plain which typically involves repetitive soil tillage at similar depth. Runoff and erosion easily occur at higher altitude plain areas

Drivers: climate, land management

Time projection: 2010-2040; 2040-2070; 2070-2100

Output: In this study effects of subsoil compaction, overland flow following surface compaction and erosion were simulated for six soil series in the Destra Sele area in Italy, including effects of climate change. Result as water-limited yield (Yw) considering simulated effect of soil compaction

Verburg et al. 2012

An assessment of the impact of climate adaptation measures to reduce flood risk on ecosystem services

DESCRIPTION: The methodology for assessing land use changes is based on a multi-scale, multi-model approach that integrates the economic, demographic, and environmental drivers of land change in a consistent modelling framework. Global scale drivers of land use change originating from changes in demography, consumption patterns, economic development, trade, and climate change are analysed with the combined application of the global economy model LEITAP and the global integrated assessment model IMAGE. The core of the modelling framework including the land allocation model and the indicator models are integrated into a consistent modelling interface called the CLUE-Scanner. The land allocation model is the Dyna-CLUE model (Verburg and Overmars 2009) using the numerical algorithms of the Land Use Scanner model (Koomen et al. 2008)

Drivers: climate, land use, land management

Time projection: 2030

Reference scenario of IPCC-SRESS (IPCC2000) elaborated for the European conditions by Westhoek et al., 2006. The scenario accounts for global scale drivers influencing EU land use like: increasing food and feed demand in emerging countries (BRIC), changing trade regimes because of competitiveness, changing environmental constraints because of resource scarcity and climate change (IMAGE model), demographic changes. Population EU-27 in 2030: 500 million; population change since 2000: 4%; EU-15 GDP yearly growth: 1,3%; EU-12 GDP yearly growth: 3,4%; trade of agricultural products: export subsidies and import tariffs phased out. Slight increase in non-tariff barriers. Product quota phased out and abolished in 2020. Farm payments decoupled fully and gradually reduced by 50% in 2030. Intervention prices phased out and abolished by 2030

Output: The flood risk indicator highlights the urban areas within the potential flooding zone that are newly developed since 2000. New urban land cover identified by the land allocation model is overlaid with a map of future flood-prone areas (100-year return period) under conditions of climate change. This assessment of potential river-flood risk does not incorporate the conditions of flood defence systems and the effects of upstream land use change on flood occurrence. Therefore, the indicator is especially meant to highlight those areas where new assets become exposed to flood risk. Flood risk from the sea is not included in the analysis. To some extent this expansion of agricultural land in Eastern Europe takes place at the cost of fallow land and small patches of (semi)natural land within the main agricultural areas. Deforestation may be a more important issue for countries that have experienced expropriation in the 1950s and where the forest has been transferred back to the initial owners in the 1990s, leading to very small, fragmented ownership structures which favour deforestation. The indicators of biodiversity and carbon sequestration are used to investigate if the adaptation measures lead to synergies with other ecosystem services. Overall, the differences resulting from the adaptation measures at the level of administrative regions are small. Many of the local impacts are compensated within the same administrative unit and therefore do not show in the map. At the same time the differences between the scenarios should not be ignored: depending on the region the impacts can be considerable

Polce et al. 2016

Global change impacts on ecosystem services: a spatially explicit assessment for Europe

DESCRIPTION: ESs are derived from CML (which itself uses the A1B emission scenario) for both scenarios (CML), LUC states are also derived for both scenarios from LUISA, each ESs is linked to LUC and the scenarios are then compared.

Drivers: climate, land management

Time projection: 2050

Output: Northern Europe (Scandinavia) showed the largest difference in both negative erosion control, and positive erosion control. Positive control in great areas of the Italian Peninsula. They look at changes in ES for areas without change in LUC (they call this climate-driven change) and observed that results are quite different to those when both LUC and climate changed

3.2 Questionnaire Responses

A total of 379 filled questionnaires from 15 countries were gathered and analysed. The majority of responses came from Portugal (208), followed by Italy (39), Austria (27), Slovakia (25), and Lithuania (21) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2 - Distribution of filled questionnaires by country

Very few answers were received from Policy makers (Fig. 3), with most of the completed questionnaires coming from Organizations, Farmers, and technical experts of public administration (*Other* in Fig. 3).

Figure 3 - Distribution of stakeholder responses by category

Among the SESs that should be protected (Fig. 4), “Hydrological control” (76%), “Habitat for biodiversity” (76%), and “Erosion control” (76%) are considered *very important*, whereas “Pest and disease control”, “Pollution control”, “Biomass production”, and “GHG and climate regulation” show higher percentages for *important* and *slightly important*.

Figure 4 - Degree of importance of SESs.

Regarding ST (Fig. 5), “Soil erosion” (75%), “Soil drought” (64%), “Soil sealing” (63%), and “SOC loss” (63%) are considered the most important for agricultural soils, and “Soil acidification”, “Waterlogging”, and “Salinization” are considered less important.

Figure 5 - Degree of importance of ST

Regarding the importance of drivers of change in affecting soil health (Fig. 6), “Land cover/use change” and “Land management” received the highest percentages for *very important* (69%), while “Climate change” and “Population growth” are ranked as less important.

Figure 6 - Degree of importance of drivers of change

2030 is the time scale most relevant to stakeholders (Fig.7) with 64% of preferences, whereas 2100 is considered less relevant as a time scale.

Figure 7 - Relevance of time scale to stakeholders

70% of stakeholders consider it *very necessary* to contribute to keeping temperature increases below 2°C (Fig. 8), and 63% *strongly agree* both to limit the consumption of agricultural land due to soil sealing (Fig. 9) and to take restoration actions on degraded soils (Fig. 10).

Figure 8 - Preferences as to actions to take to contribute to keeping rise in temperature below 2°C

Figure 9 - Preferences as to actions to take to limit soil sealing of agricultural soils

Figure 10 - Preferences as to restoration actions to make on degraded soils

Regarding the adoption of agricultural practices to improve soil health, the majority of preferences *strongly agree* that it is worth adopting practices to maintain or improve SOC content (Fig. 11) and 66% *strongly agree* on the need to adopt more soil-conserving measures (Fig. 12), but less than 40% agree to expand land under organic management (Fig. 13).

Figure 11 - Preferences as to agricultural practices to adopt, to maintain or improve SOC content

Figure 2 - Preferences on the need to adopt soil-conservation management measures

Figure 3 - Preferences as to actions to take to expand area of land under organic management

Regarding the questions about stakeholder’s capacity to modify strategies, policies or agricultural practices to adapt to environmental changes (Fig. 14 and 15), answers show a different trend compared to the previous ones, with percentages more evenly distributed between the scales and higher percentages for the Not Applicable category (N/A).

Figure 12 - Stakeholders capacity to adapt to environmental changes by modifying strategies and policies

Figure 13 - Stakeholders capacity to adapt to environmental changes by modifying agricultural practices

Unlike capacity to modify habits or activities, stakeholder willingness to modify habits or activities to improve and protect soil health shows clearer trends towards *high* (44%) and *very high* values (42%) (Fig. 16).

Figure 14 - Stakeholders willingness to modify habits or activities to improve and protect soil health

4 Conclusions

The activities outlined in this report resulted in the selection of a group of scenarios of change, that were presented to stakeholders to inform them about the effects that climate change, demographic trends, and land cover/use and land management changes could produce in agricultural soils. Their opinions were then asked for, to co-construct which actions should be adopted to mitigate these effects.

Although SERENA and EJP SOIL project stakeholder lists were used, and stakeholders were contacted directly by the project partners and the EJP SOIL National Communication Representatives, stakeholders' participation in the questionnaire was quite weak. An extraordinary number of responses came from Portugal, and a fairly good number of responses came from Italy, Austria, Slovakia, and Lithuania, but very few answers were received from other countries involved in the project, and from some even no responses at all.

Despite these issues, some considerations can be drawn from the results obtained.

Regarding SESs and STs, it seems that stakeholders perceive some SESs as priorities to be protected and some STs as more important for land degradation processes. The same trend applies to drivers of change, where climate change and population growth seem to worry stakeholders less than changes in land use or land management. The time scale considered most relevant for stakeholders is "Near future", and this is in line with the mid-term target for MS (e.g., EU Soil Strategy and Agenda 2030).

Stakeholders agree on limiting the expansion of soil sealing to the detriment of agricultural soils, as well as on implementing actions to limit the increase in temperature, on taking restoration actions on degraded soils, or on adopting agricultural practices to improve the SOC content. The percentage on the degree of importance drops if it involves taking actions to expand the extent of land under organic

management. In the open responses, this reluctance was attributed to unsustainable yield reductions both for producers and to meet global food needs, no market, and a greater interest in investments to reduce the impacts of "conventional" agriculture.

Questions regarding the capacity of stakeholders to make changes also show an interesting summary. On the one hand, there is a fairly high value in the desire to modify one's activities to improve soil health, while on the other hand there is an inability of organizations to put these changes into practice.

The results indicate that consideration must be given to how best to raise awareness among stakeholders on some aspects of soil health – the importance of all SESs and STs for maintaining soil health, and the importance of organic farming strategy for its multiple benefits on ecosystem services as also promoted by the EU's Farm-to-Fork and the Biodiversity Strategy. These points take on new significance in light of the indications contained in the new EU Soil Law but must also take into consideration the provisions given by the UNCBD and the UNCCD.

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Appendix 1 - The Excel sheet with the collection of selected documents.

The complete Excel sheet can be found at: https://creagov.sharepoint.com/:x:/r/sites/SERENAEJP-SOIL/Documenti%20condivisi/General/WP1/Deliverable%201.4/Appendix1_D1.4.xlsx?d=wcead3a584aca412d9518327349237031&csf=1&web=1&e=qAGcXj

(in the final report, the file might be linked from somewhere else)

Appendix 2 - Print version of complete questionnaire

The complete Pdf file can be found at: <https://creagov.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/SERENAEJP-SOIL/Documenti%20condivisi/General/WP1/Deliverable%201.4?csf=1&web=1&e=S6dF8a>

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